

SITE GS/SPHINX	DATE 7/15/79	AREA NE	SQUARE N3/W1	PAGE
 Feature No.	Coordinates:		Levels	
			Top: ≈ 10.64	Bottom: ≈ 10.47
	DIMENSIONS			
Diameter: 15 cm	Width:	Length:	Depth: 17 cm	

Locus	Mat.	Color	Hard.	Consis.	Pottery	Inclusions	
①	SAND (OR CLAY?) (Fine) / GYPSUM Matrix	Buff to Light Tan	Compact	Fine to powdery on drying	T Small Fragments ★	Lm ✓ Small frags and particles	Gp ✓
					D	Gr ✓ Small frags ★	Char
						Do	
						Ba	
						Al	
						Other	
** ②	CLAY (?)	Grey (Light)	Packed	slightly grainy to fine + powdery on drying	T * 6-10	Lm ✓ frags & particles	Gp
					D 6-10	Gr ✓ Large frags packed "granite dust"	Char ✓ ? ††
						Dolerite OR	Chert 5 frags
						Ba ✓ few small chips †	FLINT 4 small flakes
						Al	
						Other 2 Grey mud-like spots	
** 2a	GYPSUM CLAY + fine sand	Greyish to Beige	Packed slightly more than ②	grainy to fine powdery on drying	T 0	Lm ✓ small frags and particles	Gp ✓ ?
					D	Gr ✓ "	Char
						Do ✓ Diorite small chips - few	
						Ba	
						Al	
						Other	
③	SAND (Quartz)	TAN	Loose	grainy	T 0	Lm	Gp
					D	Gr	Char
						Do	
						Ba	
						Al	
						Other	
○					T	Lm	Gp
					D	Gr	Char
						Do	
						Ba	
						Al	
						Other	

PHOTOGRAPH	Color: Roll/ C3 C4	No. 26, 27, 29, 30, 31 1, 2,	B&W: Roll/ 3	No. 13, 14, 15, 16, 17 18, 19.
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DRAWN	Area Plan: Plotted 1:20	Feature Plan: 1:10 Plan of surface U. FH14-415	Sections: 1:2 section N-S
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REMARKS; INTERPRETATION: ★ Large sherds packed in fill ② showing through surface
 ① - Also large granite fragments
 * Large, fragile sherds make up part. of O.K. type CRW vessel
 ** ① Slightly darker - more tan than ②
 † Most of small chips - dark grey to black - look to be diorite (crystalline) but some prob. basalt-dolerite
 †† ② Sifted - very fine powdery - has minute black flecks, some of which diorite-granite particles, but some →

may be carbon.

** (2a) NOT appreciably diff. than (2) but seems to have gypsum slightly more packed, chalky, & beige - yet dries out to look much like (2) and has granite etc. particles and small frags.

(3) Less than .05 at bottom